

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

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Coordination and Support Action

*Extended Practice Abstract - Assessing the profitability of
investments in the short food supply chain in a nutshell*
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1. Introduction

Farmers interested in the short food supply chain (SFSC) are advised to assess the profitability of their investment ideas prior to their implementation. In other words, they should seek to answer the question of whether the investment pays off. Simple calculation methods such as the net present value method, the internal rate of return method, and the dynamic amortisation calculation can support farmers in their decision-making as they allow to evaluate the profitability of investments (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021). The different calculation methods are briefly summarised in this document. In addition, an example of a calculation is presented and literature references for further readings are included.

2. Dynamic investment calculation methods

Dynamic investment calculation methods consider the cash flows generated by the investment over the period of its usage, for instance, the total period over which an on-farm shop will be operated. Considering the whole period is important as larger investments require long-term capital planning (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021)

Farmers interested in investment calculations need to gather the following information:

- How high are the investment costs?
- Which in and out-going payments can be expected?
- How long is the useful lifespan, and how are the payments distributed over this period?
- How should the asset be financed? What are the interest rates for equity and debt?

The information above is used to determine the value of the payments in the current time period by discounting future payments. The periods are to be considered individually since a payment received today is worth more than future payments of the same amount (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021).

2.1 Net present value method

The first method is the net present value method. It calculates the present value of all expected cash flows generated by an investment, subtracts the initial investment cost, and provides a single number that represents the net value of the investment in today's Euros. This net value is determined by calculating the net difference between the in- and out-going payments and by discounting them (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021).

To discount the payments per period (k) the difference between the in- and out-going payments is multiplied with the so-called discount factor (DSF). The DSF is calculated for each period and considers the interest rate i (which is expressed as a decimal number, for example, 0.05 if the interest rate is 5 %), and the period k :

$$DSF = (1+i)^{-k}$$

The net present value (C_0) is the sum of the investment costs and all discounted net payments (in-going payments are denoted with e_k , out-going payments with a_k):

$$C_0 = A_0 - \sum_{k=1}^n (e_k - a_k) \times (1 + i)^{-k} + R \times (1 + i)^{-n}$$

The initial investment costs (acquisition payment (A_0)) are also considered and do not need to be discounted. In case a residual value (R) can be achieved at the end of the period of usage (n), it is also discounted and considered in the calculation.¹

A positive net present value shows that the investment is profitable. In turn, a negative net present value indicates that the investment might not be profitable. The value itself displays the amount of money a farmer earns after covering all the expected costs (investment costs and running costs, and interest rates) (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021).

The interest rate used to determine the DSF should reflect the farmer's opportunity costs. In case farmers use their own equity, the interest rate they receive for savings should be used. In case money is borrowed, the interest rate for the credit is considered. Usually, farmers use both equity and debt financing, and a mixed calculation is necessary (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021).²

Table 1 provides an example of the net present value calculation. In the example the initial payment for the investment is €100,000 in period k_0 . The investment is assumed to be used for ten years, the annual in-going payments from selling products are €20,000, the annual out-going payments (e.g., running costs) are €5,000. Products can be sold in the first year after the investment was made, the residual value is €2,500. The net present value is €23,352 and it is determined by summing up the investment payment and the discounted net payments ($i=0.04$) (column six – discounted net payments).

In the example, it is assumed that only the investment is made in k_0 , and no other in- and out-going payments occur. In practice, this is the case if a construction is initially carried out in period zero, but the investment can only be used in the following year.

¹ Since the investment costs are already considered, no depreciation needs to be included in the net payments.

² The appropriate interest rate used in the DSF calculation should be calculated considering both interest rates when a farmer uses both equity and debt financing. For example, if a farmer uses 30% equity with an interest rate of 3%, and 70% debt financing with an interest rate of 5%, the appropriate interest rate for discounting would be 4.4% (or 0.044 as the decimal number). This is calculated from the shares of debt and equity and the interest rates: $0.30 \times 0.03 + 0.70 \times 0.05 = 0.044$.

Table 1 Example of the net present value calculation for an investment in a machine (Source: own calculation)^a.

Period (k)	In-going payments (e _k)	Out-going payments (a _k)	Net payments (K _t = e _k -a _k)	DSF (DSF = (1+i) ^{-k})	Discounted net payments
0		100,000 €	-100,000 €	1.00	-100,000 €
1	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.96	14,423 €
2	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.92	13,868 €
3	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.89	13,335 €
4	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.85	12,822 €
5	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.82	12,329 €
6	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.79	11,855 €
7	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.76	11,399 €
8	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.73	10,960 €
9	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.70	10,539 €
10	22,500.00€	5,000 €	17,500 €	0.68	11,822 €

^a In the example, constant in- and out-going payments are considered. Due to price fluctuations this may not be realistic. Farmers can adjust annual in- and out-going payments if they can quantify the fluctuations.

2.2 The internal rate of return

The internal rate of return describes the interest rate to be expected on the capital employed. It can be determined by increasing the interest rate used for discounting until the net present value of the investment is zero. It can also be calculated directly in Excel by using the function IRR (Microsoft, 2023). When using the function IRR, it is important that the cash flow is used before discounting (column four in Table 1).

An investment is profitable when the internal rate of return exceeds the interest rate that is used for discounting. Using the function IRR, an internal rate of return of 8.4% (decimal number: 0.084) is found for the example in Table 1. This shows that the internal rate of return exceeds the interest rate of 0.04 that was used for discounting the payments and hence that the investment is profitable.

2.3 The dynamic amortisation calculation

The dynamic amortisation calculation provides information on the riskiness of the investment. It shows the period (k) in which the payment has paid off (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021). In Table 2 the discounted payments are summed up period by period (column seven – cumulative discounted net payments). This

shows that the net capital value becomes positive in period eight for the first time. In case investments do not reach a positive capital value during their whole period of usage, they are not profitable.

Table 2 Example for the amortisation period for an investment in a machine (Source: own calculation).

Period (k)	In-going payments (e_k)	Out-going payments (a_k)	Net difference ($K_t = e_k - a_k$)	DSF (DSF = $(1+i)^{-k}$)	Discounted net payments	Cumulative discounted net payments
0		100,000 €	-100,000€	1.00	-100,000 €	-100,000 €
1	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.96	14,423 €	-85,577 €
2	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.92	13,868 €	-71,709 €
3	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.89	13,335 €	-58,374 €
4	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.85	12,822 €	-45,552 €
5	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.82	12,329 €	-33,223 €
6	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.79	11,855 €	-21,368 €
7	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.76	11,399 €	-9,969 €
8	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.73	10,960 €	991 €
9	20,000 €	5,000 €	15,000 €	0.70	10,539 €	11,530 €
10	22,500.00€	5,000 €	17,500 €	0.68	11,822 €	23,352 €

When comparing two investment alternatives with similar net present values, the investment that pays off sooner would be favoured, as this investment entails lower risks (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021).

3. Example I – Investment in a mobile layer hen barn with direct sales of eggs

A simple example is provided below for a hypothetical farmer interested in investing in a layer hen barn coupled with direct marketing of eggs.

An organic farmer is interested in investing in a mobile layer hen barn with 300 places for layer hens. An example of such a barn is shown in picture 1.

Picture 1 Mobile layer hen barn (Source: Adobe Stocks, 2023)

Before purchasing the barn, he seeks to determine whether the barn is profitable and if so under which circumstances. He is especially interested to find out if he needs to sell eggs over the SFSC to run the layer hen barn profitably.

As a first step, he seeks to determine the expected investment costs, the expected out-going payments and the expected in-going payments. He determines the expected investment costs by searching online for possible barns. The expected investment costs are €179 per hen place (in total €53,700), and the usage period is described to be 12 years.

The expected in- and out-going payments can also be determined by searching online for, e.g., contribution margin calculations or even full cost accounting calculations. The farmer finds data on the websites of farmer associations and research institutes. Data from LEL (2023) is used for the calculations below.

The expected in-going payments depend on the laying performance of the hens, the egg price, and the share of eggs sold over different sales channels. He determines the expected sales price for eggs by talking to other farmers about prices paid at producer organisations. In addition, he visits existing on-farm shops and looks for egg prices paid at supermarkets that advertise regionally produced products. When the farmer sells all his eggs via a producer organisation, he would receive 19 cents per egg. For the layer hens, it is assumed that the hens can be sold for €1 per animal after their usage period of 12 months.

The expected out-going payments are the production costs, for instance, feeding costs, veterinary service costs and insurance costs. Since the farmer is busy, he decides that all work will be conducted by external workers, which causes costs of €14.00 per hour.¹ Since the farmer wants to set up the mobile barn on an unused parcel of grassland, no rental costs for the land are included.

After collecting the data, he builds an excel spreadsheet holding the expected in- and out-going. The in-going payments are e.g., the expected revenue for the eggs, and layer hens at the end of their life. Table 3 shows the expected in-going payments, Table 4 the expected out-going payments.

Table 3 Expected in-going payments per year (Source: own calculation).

In-going payments	
Revenue old animals (300 hens; €1 per hen, useful life hen: one year)	€ 300.00
Revenue eggs (19 cents per egg for 79,440 eggs (80 % laying performance, 331 laying days))	€ 15,093.60
Annual in-going payments	€ 15,393.60

¹ Imputed costs such as the entrepreneur's profit entitlement and wages for family workers are not taken into account in the calculation.

Table 4 Expected out-going payments per year (Source: own calculation).

Out-going payments	
Feed (roughage and hen feed)	€ 8,124.00
Veterinarian and medicine	€ 48.00
Insurance	€ 93.24
Energy and Water	€ 360.00
Litter costs	€ 70.80
Machine costs (variable)	€ 300.00
Spreading of manure	€ 9.00
Advertising services	€ 30.00
Young hens	€ 3,300.00
Replacement of young hens (12 % losses)	€ 396.00
Working hours (480 h per year, 14 € per hour (egg collection, moving the mobile, cleaning etc.))	€ 6,720.00
Annual maintenance (2 % of the acquisition costs)	€ 1,074.00
Annual out-going payment	€ 20,525.04

The farmer calculates the net present value of the barn using the expected investment costs and the expected in- and out-going payments (Table 5). The estimated net present value is -103,785 € when it is assumed that he sells all his eggs via the producer organisation.

The expected investment costs are considered in the first period when he purchases the barn. The barn can be used right from the start and annual in-and out-going payments are thus also expected in period zero. The interest rate i is 0.04.

Table 5 Net present value calculation for a barn with 300 organic layer hens (Source: own calculation).

Period (k)	at (out-going payments)	et (in-going payments)	Net payments (Kt=et - at)	DSF	Discounted net payments
0	€ 74,225.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 58,831.44	1	-€ 58,831.44
1	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.96	-€ 4,934.08
2	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.92	-€ 4,744.30
3	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.89	-€ 4,561.83
4	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.85	-€ 4,386.38
5	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.82	-€ 4,217.67
6	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.79	-€ 4,055.45
7	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.76	-€ 3,899.47
8	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.73	-€ 3,749.49
9	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.70	-€ 3,605.28
10	€ 20,525.04	€ 15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.68	-€ 3,466.62
11	€ 20,525.04	€15,393.60	-€ 5,131.44	0.65	-€ 3,333.29

The farmer knows that he cannot operate the mobile barn profitably when selling via the producer organisation and would like to sell his eggs directly to consumers for 50 cents per egg at his farm. The farm itself is located on a busy street but larger urban centres are further away. The farmer thus assumes that he can sell only 50% of the eggs at the farm. In addition, he would like to sell 40% of the eggs to the supermarket. He talks to his local supermarket, and they offer to sell a share of his eggs and pay him 35 cents per egg. The remaining eggs will be sold via the producer organisation for 19 cents per egg. Overall, he calculates an average egg price of 41 cents, and the in-going payments increase to almost €33,000 (Table 6).

Table 6 Expected in-going payments per year when eggs are sold over the SFSC (Source: own calculation).

In-going payments	
Revenue old animals (300 hens; 1 € per hen, useful life of the chickens one year)	€ 300.00
Revenue eggs (41 ct per egg on average)	€ 32,490.96
Annual in-going payments	€ 32,790.96

In his new calculation, additional investment costs for the on-farm shop need to be considered. An extensive on-farm shop describes a setting where no staff works in the shop. This could comprise of a simple garden

hut and is self-serviced. The cost of the extensive farm shop is €2,000 (e.g., a garden hut, with light, shelves, and signs). Next to the additional investment costs, the farmer includes labour costs for packing and the costs for packaging materials in the out-going payments, as these increase when eggs are sold directly to supermarkets or on-farm. The labour needed increases by 0.15 minutes per egg when he sells via the local supermarket and 0.25 minutes per egg when an egg is sold on-farm. The packaging costs are 0.03 cents per egg both for the supermarket and for the on-farm shop. He calculates that the annual outgoing payments increase to be €26,000 (Table 7).

Table 7 Expected out-going payments per year when eggs are sold over the SFSC (Source: own calculation).

Out-going payments	
Feed (roughage and hen feed)	€ 8,124.00
Veterinarian and medicine	€ 48.00
Insurance	€ 93.24
Energy and Water	€ 360.00
Litter costs	€ 70.80
Var. machine costs	€ 300.00
Spreading of manure	€ 9.00
Advertising services	€ 30.00
Young hens	€ 3,300.00
Replacement of young hens (12 % losses)	€ 396.00
Working hours (480 h per year, 14 € per hour (egg collection, moving the mobile, cleaning etc.))	€ 6,720.00
Annual maintenance (2 % of the acquisition costs)	€ 1,074.00
Direct marketing costs (Packaging, 0.03 cents per egg sold over the SFSC)	€ 2,144.88
Direct marketing costs (working hours)	€ 3,429.16
Annual out-going payments	€ 26,099.08

The net present value calculation is shown in Table 8. The barn can be run profitably when eggs are sold over the SFSC, the capital value is positive €9,600, and the internal rate of return is 7.5%, and thus above the

interest rate used for discounting (4%). The barn would pay-off after ten years. However, the additional earnings generated over the twelve years are low (€9,600).

Table 8 Net present value for the layer barn with direct marketing (SFSC) (Source: own calculation).

Period (k)	In-going payments (e_k)	Out-going payments (a_k)	Net difference ($K_t = e_k - a_k$)	DSF (DSF = $(1+i)^{-k}$)	Discounted net differences	Cumulative payments
0	€ 81,799.08	€ 32,790.96	-€ 49,008.12	1	-€ 49,008.12	
1	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.96	€ 6,434.50	-€ 42,573.62
2	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.92	€ 6,187.02	-€ 36,386.60
3	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.89	€ 5,949.06	-€ 30,437.54
4	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.85	€ 5,720.25	-€ 24,717.30
5	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.82	€ 5,500.24	-€ 19,217.06
6	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.79	€ 5,288.69	-€ 13,928.37
7	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.76	€ 5,085.28	-€ 8,843.09
8	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.73	€ 4,889.69	-€ 3,953.40
9	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.70	€ 4,701.63	€ 748.23
10	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.68	€ 4,520.79	€ 5,269.02
11	€ 26,099.08	€ 32,790.96	€ 6,691.88	0.65	€ 4,346.92	€ 9,615.94

Overall, the example seeks to show that farmers need to consider the production costs of all products that they intend to sell over the SFSC in investment calculations and not only additional costs caused by direct marketing.

4. Example II – Considerations necessary for other investments in SFSC sales channels

The first example shows that farmers need to consider the costs of growing/producing the products sold over their SFSC sales channels, and the costs associated with the sales channels in their profitability calculations.

The net present value method and the methods building on the net present value calculation (internal rate of return, dynamic amortisation calculation) consider in- and out-going payments. Contributing margin accounting for the products are a good starting point for farmers to evaluate the costs of production that are part of the out-going payments.¹ When the profitability of sales channels, for instance an on-farm shop, is evaluated only the costs caused by the products sold via the shop should be considered. When farmers are also interested in investing in new types of production (e.g., layer hens), separate investment calculations for layer hen production itself are needed and should consider all possible sales channels. Furthermore, the costs caused by the marketing activities over the SFSC chain need to be included in the out-going payments:

- For on-farm shops, these might be labour costs and costs for packaging
- For farmers' markets, market fees and costs for traveling need to be considered

Information on the necessary investment costs can be evaluated by determining what inventory is necessary:

- For on-farm shops, costs can occur from rebuilding a barn, building a new shop, building a parking area, building consumer toilets, building cold storage warehouse, buying smaller refrigerators, shelves, fixed marketing material (e.g., signs in front of the shop, for advertisement), a cash register system...
- For farmers' markets different settings can be differentiated, there are stands with tables only, but vans that have a cooling system and where products are sold directly via a side flap are also an option.

When determining the in-going payments farmers could consider prices at other SFSC sales points as a starting point. For revenues, the number of products sold is of importance and farmers need to carefully consider consumer turn up that can be determined by their location. This is also shown in example I, where the farmer assumes that he can only sell half of the eggs produced on-farm. Extensive on-farm shops without

¹ When considering the production costs, the results of the net present value method show how much sales through direct marketing over SFSC contribute to the farm's earnings. An alternative option would be to consider opportunity costs (the prices achieved by the products when they are sold over existing sales channels). This way the results show whether direct sales would be a profitable sales alternative. However, this is a deviation from the classical method, since no imputed costs are considered in the net present value method.

staff or simple farmers' market stands might be a cheaper starting point for farmers to determine the consumer turn up prior to an investment in more expensive set-ups.

Some SFSC sales channels can also influence the harvesting volumes and hence the revenue. For community-supported agriculture and pick-your-own settings, smaller harvesting amounts and larger losses occur because consumers are less experienced in harvesting activities. Farmers therefore also need to keep in mind if direct marketing affects their production processes.

5. Additional examples and information

- An example of a **simplified profitability calculation** is presented by Bruch and Ernst (2010). They provide an example of how a farmer already selling on farmers' markets could evaluate whether it is profitable for him to grow and sell additional tomatoes for a regional restaurant.
- LeRoux (2016) provides information on advantages and disadvantages of commonly known marketing channels and costs commonly associated with them.
- In a German guideline, Rettner (2018) provides an **overview of investment costs** necessary for different SFSC marketing activities (e.g., direct delivery setups, farmers' market stand, on-farm shops), and on common margins achieved through direct marketing activities.

6. Critical evaluation of the methods

Since investment calculations consider expected payments, they are always bound to uncertainty. Farmers need to put effort into searching for appropriate information, as the quality of the predictions will depend on the data used. However, investment calculations allow a simplification of reality and lower the complexity of decision problems. Because of this beneficial aspect, they are believed to be the best available method to predict profitability of future investments (Poggensee and Poggensee, 2021).

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